

PREDICTION OF MAGNETOELECTRIC COUPLING AND EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF INTELLIGENT MATERIALS: PIEZOELECTRIC/PIEZOMAGNETIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A unified method based on the inclusion formulation is proposed to determine the magnetic, electric and elastic fields in a composite with piezoelectric and piezomagnetic phases. The composite reinforcements are treated as ellipsoidal inclusions that enable the reinforcement geometries ranging from thin flakes to continuous fibers. Utilizing the proposed method, the magneto-electro-elastic tensors analogous to Eshelby tensors for elastic ellipsoidal inclusions are obtained. With these tensors, the magnetic, electric and elastic fields around the inclusion as well as concentration factors are determined. Furthermore, based upon the Mori-Tanaka mean field theory to account for the interaction between inclusions and matrix, the effective magneto-electro-elastic constants (elastic moduli, piezoelectric coefficients, dielectric constants, piezomagnetic coefficients, magnetoelectric, and magnetic permeability) of the composites are expressed explicitly in terms of phase properties, volume fraction, and inhomogeneity shape. The numerical examinations have been conducted for the three-dimensional BaTiO₃-CoFe₂O₄ composite, and the overall composite behavior have been examined numerically. It is found that the composite reveals interesting magnetoelectric coupling which is absent in each constituent.

KEYWORDS: magneto-electro-elastic Eshelby tensor, anisotropic inclusion method, magnetoelectric coupling effect, Mori-Tanaka theory.

INTRODUCTION

The present paper is to develop a unified and explicit method for determining the magneto-electro-elastic fields around an ellipsoidal inclusion and the effective properties of a piezoelectric/piezomagnetic composite. The inclusions and the matrix are assumed to be perfectly bonded, without any sliding, void nucleation, or growth on their interfaces. The proposed method is based on the anisotropic inclusion method [1] in elasticity in a manner analogous to the that for uncoupled magnetic, electric, and elastic behavior. With this method, the expression for the coupled elastic, electric, and magnetic fields around an ellipsoidal inclusion is expressed in the unified form of surface integral. Then, a unified expression for the magneto-electro-elastic tensors analogous to Eshelby [2] tensors for elastic ellipsoidal inclusions is obtained. The resulting magneto-electro-elastic fields and Eshelby tensors can further be applied to obtain magneto-electro-elastic concentration factors. Finally, based on the Mori-Tanaka [3] theory to account for interaction at finite concentrations of inclusions, the effective elastic moduli, piezoelectric coefficients, dielectric constants,

piezomagnetic coefficients, magnetoelectric, and magnetic permeability of the composite in terms of phase properties, volume fraction, and inclusions' shape are presented in closed forms.

CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

Consider a composite material with piezoelectric and piezomagnetic phases. Suppose that the elastic displacement vector u_i , the electric potential ϕ , and the magnetic potential ψ are chosen as independent variables, while the dependent variables are the elastic stress tensor σ_{ij} , the electric displacement vector D_i , and the magnetic induction B_i . Due to the coupled interaction between the two phases, the constitutive equations coupled the deformations, electric fields, and magnetic fields are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijmn}\epsilon_{mn} - e_{nij}E_n - q_{nij}H_n, \\ D_i &= e_{imn}\epsilon_{mn} + \kappa_{in}E_n + \lambda_{ni}H_n \\ B_i &= q_{imn}\epsilon_{mn} + \lambda_{in}E_n + \Gamma_{in}H_n,\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{mn} is elastic strain tensor, E_n electric field, H_n magnetic field, C_{ijmn} elastic moduli, e_{nij} piezoelectric coefficient, q_{nij} piezomagnetic coefficient, κ_{in} dielectric constant, and Γ_{in} magnetic permeability. The magnetoelectric coefficient λ_{in} is a new material property of the composite, since it is not present in the constituents.

To treat the elastic, electric and magnetic variables on equal footing, Eq. (1) is compactly expressed in the following shorthand notation as

$$\Sigma_{ij} = L_{iJMn}Z_{Mn}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\Sigma_{ij} = \begin{cases} \sigma_{ij} & J \leq 3, \\ D_i & J = 4, \\ B_i & J = 5, \end{cases} \quad Z_{Mn} = \begin{cases} \epsilon_{mn} = (u_{m,n} + u_{n,m})/2 & M \leq 3, \\ -E_n = \phi_{,n} & M = 4, \\ -H_n = \psi_{,n} & M = 5. \end{cases} \quad (3.a)$$

$$L_{iJMn} = \begin{cases} C_{ijmn} & J, M \leq 3, \\ e_{nij} & J \leq 3, M = 4, \\ q_{nij} & J \leq 3, M = 5, \\ e_{imn} & J = 4, M \leq 3, \\ -\kappa_{in} & J = 4, M = 4, \\ -\lambda_{in} & J = 4, M = 5; J = 5, M = 4, \\ q_{imn} & J = 5, M \leq 3, \\ -\Gamma_{in} & J = 5, M = 5, \end{cases} \quad (3.b)$$

Throughout this paper, conventional indicial notation is used where repeated lowercase subscripts are summed over 1 to 3, while uppercase subscripts are summed over 1 to 5. For example, $T_j U_j = T_1 U_1 + T_4 U_4 + T_5 U_5$, where $j = 1 \rightarrow 3$.

COUPLED MAGNETO-ELECTRO-ELASTIC FIELDS INSIDE AN ELLIPSOIDAL INCLUSION

Consider a three dimensional, infinitely extended composite D which consists of piezoelectric and a piezomagnetic phases. This composite exhibit a magnetoelectric effect that is entirely absent in the two phases. In order to have a unified analysis, both phases will be assumed piezomagnetoelastic. Let the matrix with magneto-electro-elastic moduli L_{iJMn} contain an ellipsoidal inclusion defined by

$$\Omega: \frac{x_1^2}{a_1^2} + \frac{x_2^2}{a_2^2} + \frac{x_3^2}{a_3^2} \leq 1, \quad (4)$$

where a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 are the lengths of the semiaxes of the ellipsoid. The consideration that the shape of the inclusion is ellipsoidal enables the model to treat composite reinforcement geometries ranging from thin flakes to continuous fiber reinforcement. The composite is allowed to undergo an eigenstrain ϵ_{mn}^* (or stress-free transformation strain), eigenelectric field E_n^* (or electric displacement-free electric field), and eigenmagnetic field H_n^* (or magnetic induction-free magnetic field) in the inclusion, while subject to the constraints of the surrounding matrix. Designate Z_{Mn}^* as the unified form of the eigenstrain ϵ_{mn}^* , eigenelectric field E_n^* , and eigenmagnetic field H_n^* :

$$Z_{Mn}^* = \begin{cases} \epsilon_{mn}^* & M \leq 3, \\ -E_n^* & M = 4, \\ -H_n^* & M = 5. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

It is noted that the eigenfield Z_{Mn}^* is zero in the matrix $D - \Omega$. The eigenfield generally induces elastic displacement, electric potential, and magnetic potential, :

$$U_M = \begin{cases} u_m & M \leq 3, \\ \phi & M = 4, \\ \psi & M = 5. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Then, the corresponding stress, electric displacement, and magnetic induction, Σ_{ij} , can be obtained from the linear constitutive equation (2), as

$$\Sigma_{ij} = L_{iJMn} (U_{M,n} - Z_{Mn}^*), \quad (7)$$

in which the comma denotes partial differentiation with respect to the coordinate variable whose subscript follows the comma. In the absence of body forces, free charge, and free magnetic dipole, the coupling equilibrium equation is expressed as

$$\Sigma_{ij,i} = 0. \quad (8)$$

Substitution of Eq. (7) into (8) leads to

$$L_{ijMn} U_{M,ni} = L_{ijMn} Z_{Mn,i}^* \quad (9)$$

From the preceding equation it is seen that $L_{ijMn} Z_{Mn,i}^*$ behaves like a body force, a electric charge, and a magnetic dipole in the composite.

Following the works of Huang and Yu [4] and assuming the eigenfield Z_{Mn}^* as being uniformly distributed in the ellipsoidal inclusion, the fundamental equation (9) can be solved for $U_M(\mathbf{x})$ in terms of the Green's function $G_{MJ}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$ as

$$U_M(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} L_{iJAb} Z_{Ab}^* \bar{G}_{MJin} x_n, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\bar{G}_{MJin} = \int_{-1}^1 \int_0^{2\pi} N_{MJ}(\bar{\xi}) D^{-1}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n d\theta d\bar{\xi}_3, \quad (11)$$

with $N_{MJ}(\bar{\xi})$ and $D(\bar{\xi})$ being the cofactor and the determinant of the 5×5 matrix $L_{iMJn} \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n$, respectively.

Combining Eqs. (3.a) and (10), the induced strain, electric and magnetic fields, Z_{Mn} , due to the uniform eigenfield in the inclusion are given by

$$Z_{Mn} = S_{MnAb} Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (12)$$

where S_{MnAb} are referred to as the magneto-electro-elastic Eshelby tensors for anisotropic piezoelectric/piezomagnetic composites. Equation (12) has the same features as that of the Eshelby solution for ellipsoidal inclusions in uncoupled elastic media, *i.e.*, the induced elastic strain, electric and magnetic fields inside the ellipsoidal inclusion are uniform when the prescribed eigenfield is constant. It is also seen from the preceding equation that the resulting magneto-electro-elastic Eshelby tensors are a function of the shape of ellipsoid and the magneto-electro-elastic properties of the surrounding matrix.

By substituting Eq. (12) into (7), the stress, electric displacement, and magnetic induction inside the inclusion are obtained as

$$\Sigma_{ij} = L_{ijMn} (S_{MnAb} - I_{MnAb}) Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (13)$$

where I_{MnAb} are the second order and the fourth order identity tensors, *i.e.*,

$$I_{MnAb} = \begin{cases} (\delta_{ma} \delta_{nb} + \delta_{mb} \delta_{na}) / 2 & M, A \leq 3, \\ \delta_{nb} & M = A = 4, \text{ or } M = A = 5, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In general, the expression \bar{G}_{MJin} cannot be carried out in closed form for an ellipsoidal inclusion in anisotropic media. However, it can be easily computed numerically when the integrands $N_{MJ}(\bar{\xi})$ and $D(\bar{\xi})$ are obtained. Once \bar{G}_{MJin} is evaluated, the magneto-electro-elastic fields characterized by Eqs. (10), (12) and (13) easily follow.

EFFECTIVE MAGNETO-ELECTRO-ELASTIC PROPERTIES

For obtaining the effective properties of a piezoelectric/piezomagnetic composite, we consider a sufficiently large two-phase composite D consists of randomly oriented ellipsoidal inhomogeneities Ω ($=\Omega_1 + \Omega_2 + \dots + \Omega_N$) with electro-elastic (or magneto-elastic) constants L_{iJMn}^* and volume fraction f . The surrounding matrix is denoted by $D-\Omega$ and has magneto-elastic (or electro-elastic) constants L_{iJMn} . Here $L_{iJMn} = L_{iJMn}^* = 0$ for a piezomagnetic (piezoelectric) material when one of subscripts is 4 (or 5).

To deal with such a piezoelectric-piezomagnetic composite with randomly oriented inclusions, the Mori-Tanaka mean field theory will be employed to predict the effective elastic, piezoelectric, dielectric, piezomagnetic, magnetoelectric, and magnetic permeability constants of the composite. This theory generally yields the same effective magneto-electro-elastic moduli for the cases when either a traction-electric displacement-magnetic induction or an elastic displacement-electric field-magnetic field is prescribed on the boundary of the composite [5].

The effective magneto-electro-elastic compliance of the composite can be shown as [6]

$$\bar{L}_{MniJ}^{-1} = [I_{MnAb} - f U_{MnqR}^{-1} (L_{qRAb}^* - L_{qRAb})] L_{AbiJ}^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where

$$U_{iJAb} = (L_{iJMn}^* - L_{iJMn}) [(1-f) S_{MnAb} + f I_{MnAb}] + L_{iJAb} \quad (16)$$

The effective magneto-electro-elastic moduli \bar{L}_{iJMn} calculated for the elastic displacement, electric and magnetic fields prescribed body is derived as

$$\bar{L}_{iJMn} = L_{iJAb} [I_{AbMn} + f V_{AbqR}^{-1} (L_{qRMn}^* - L_{qRMn})], \quad (17)$$

where

$$V_{iJAb} = (1-f) (L_{iJMn}^* - L_{iJMn}) S_{MnAb} + L_{iJAb} \quad (18)$$

Numerical examinations have been conducted for a $BaTiO_3$ - $CoFe_2O_4$ composite. The material constants are given as follows [7, 8]:

$BaTiO_3$ inclusion:

$$C_{11} = 166 \text{ GPa}, C_{33} = 162 \text{ GPa}, C_{44} = 43 \text{ GPa}, C_{12} = 77 \text{ GPa}, C_{13} = 78 \text{ GPa},$$

$$e_{31} = -4.4 \text{ C/m}^2, e_{33} = 18.6 \text{ C/m}^2, e_{15} = 11.6 \text{ C/m}^2,$$

$$\kappa_{11} = 11.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2, \kappa_{33} = 12.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2,$$

$$\Gamma_{11} = 5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N s}^2/\text{C}^2, \Gamma_{33} = 10.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N s}^2/\text{C}^2.$$

$CoFe_2O_4$ matrix

$$C_{11} = 286 \text{ GPa}, C_{33} = 269.5 \text{ GPa}, C_{44} = 45.3 \text{ GPa},$$

$$C_{12} = 173.0 \text{ GPa}, C_{13} = 170.5 \text{ GPa},$$

$$q_{31} = 580.3 \text{ N/Am}, q_{33} = 699.7 \text{ N/Am}, q_{15} = 550 \text{ N/Am},$$

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa_{11} &= 0.08 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2, \quad \kappa_{33} = 0.093 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2, \\ \Gamma_{11} &= -590 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Ns}^2/\text{C}^2, \quad \Gamma_{33} = 157 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Ns}^2/\text{C}^2.\end{aligned}$$

Figures 1 through 5 illustrate the effect of the inclusion shape on the resulting composite properties; the inclusion volume fraction is set at $f = 0.5$ for these figures. Figure 1 shows the predicted elastic constants against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 . Both $\bar{C}_{11}(=\bar{L}_{1111})$ and $\bar{C}_{33}(=\bar{L}_{3333})$ decrease with the ratio due to the fact that the BaTiO_3 inclusion is lower in elastic moduli than the CoFe_2O_4 matrix. Figure 2 exhibits the piezoelectric constants of the composite. Since the matrix is absent in piezoelectric effects, the piezoelectric behavior of the composite is therefore dominated by the fiber, especially for the properties along fiber direction. It can be seen that \bar{e}_{33} and $\bar{\kappa}_{33}$ increase significantly with the aspect ratio, while the \bar{e}_{15} and $\bar{\kappa}_{11}$ remain essentially unchanged. The resulting magnetic permeabilities $\bar{\Gamma}_{ij}$ of the composite are shown in Fig. 3; both decrease with the ratio. Note that $\bar{\Gamma}_{11}$ is negative and thus its absolute value is increased when the aspect ratio increases. The resulting piezomagnetic coefficients are shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that as the aspect ratio increases, both \bar{q}_{31} and \bar{q}_{33} slightly decrease, while \bar{q}_{15} significantly increases. The magnetoelastic coupling coefficients are displayed in Fig. 5, indicating that $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$ are rather small, while $\bar{\lambda}_{33}$ increases notably with the ratio.

The magnetoelastic coupling $\bar{\lambda}_{ij}$ is a unique property of the composite, since it is absent in both constituents. The results for $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$ are plotted in Fig. 6, showing that the values of $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$ are negative at $a_3/a_1=1$ and become positive when a_3/a_1 is higher than 4. As plotted in Fig. 7, the $\bar{\lambda}_{33}$ shows the same trend in its sign. However, the magnitude of $\bar{\lambda}_{33}$ is much larger than that of $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$. Both coefficients are found to vanish at $f=0$ (pure matrix) and $f=1$ (pure fiber) in which cases the materials become monolithic. The most significant coupling effect is found to occur between $f=0.8\sim 0.9$ for $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$, while the maximum values of $\bar{\lambda}_{33}$ occur approximately at $f=0.5$ for $a_3/a_1=1$ and at $f=0.9$ for $a_3/a_1=64$. Thus, this induced coupling effect is determined not only by the inclusion volume fraction, but also by the inclusion shape.

Fig. 1 The predicted composite elastic constants against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 ($f=0.5$).

Fig. 2 The predicted composite piezoelectric constants against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 ($f=0.5$).

Fig. 3 The predicted composite magnetic permeabilities against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 ($f=0.5$).

Fig. 4 The predicted composite piezomagnetic coefficients against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 ($f=0.5$).

Fig. 5 The predicted composite magnetolectric coupling against the aspect ratio a_3/a_1 ($f=0.5$).

Fig. 6 Effect of inclusion volume fraction and aspect ratio on $\bar{\lambda}_{11}$.

Fig. 7 Effect of inclusion volume fraction and aspect ratio on $\bar{\lambda}_{33}$.

CONCLUSIONS

The anisotropic inclusion method has been extended to derive the magneto-electro-elastic fields around a piezoelectric (or piezomagnetic) ellipsoidal inclusion embedded in an infinitely extended piezomagnetic (or piezoelectric) matrix. Explicit forms have been obtained for the magneto-electro-elastic Eshelby tensors. It has been shown that the magneto-electro-elastic Eshelby tensors are functions of the shape of inclusion and the properties of the surrounding matrix. When magnetoelectric coupling is absent, the resulting Eshelby tensors reduce to those for uncoupled elastic inclusion problems. In addition, it is demonstrated that the coupled magnetic field, electric field, and elastic strain inside the inclusion are constants when eigenfield is uniformly distributed in the inclusion. With the explicit expressions for magneto-electro-elastic fields in hand, a micromechanics model has been developed to predict the effective magneto-electro-elastic moduli of for the BaTiO₃-CoFe₂O₄ composite, in which the matrix is magnetostrictive. The magnetoelectric coupling is a unique effect to the composite, and how it relates to the inclusion volume fraction and aspect ratio has been discussed in detail.

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